

The Social Accident

A Theoretical Model and a Research Agenda for Studying the Influence of Social and Cultural Characteristics on Motor Vehicle Accidents

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Abstract

The paper develops a sociological model to explain collisions between two drivers or more. The “Social Accident” model presented here integrates empirical findings from prior studies and extant sociological theories. Sociological theory posits that social groups have unique cultural characteristics, which include a distinctive world view and ways of operating that influence its members. These cultural characteristics may cause drivers in different groups to interpret a given situation differently; therefore, they will make conflicting decisions that may possibly lead to road accidents. The proposed model may contribute to an understanding of the social mechanism related to interactions and communication among drivers by presenting new directions for understanding accidents and collisions. The paper concludes with suggestions for future research that will employ the model to assess its predictive and practical utility.

Key words

Sociology; Culture; Car collisions; Interaction among drivers; Group differences; Cultural influence.

1. Introduction

Research of road accidents began a hundred years ago, and, as it developed, the understanding became stronger that their cause stemmed mostly from human characteristics, whether paying insufficient attention or erring in processing information and in decision-making (see, e.g., Shinar, 1978). A large proportion of the studies and theories developed in the past to understand these factors emphasized personal characteristics and driver behavior (Elvik and Vaa, 2004). These studies dealt principally with various personality components that lead to accident proneness, risk-taking, and driving over the speed limit. Other studies analyzed attention disorders while driving, the effect of fatigue, aggressive and violent driving, gap acceptance for crossing intersections, and more.

Notwithstanding the environmental safeguards designed to protect a vehicle's occupants, the laws for controlling driving behavior (Boyce and Geller, 1999, 2002) and the determination of various bodies to reduce the number of road accidents, more than 3,000 people are killed in road accidents on the streets of the world every day (Peden et al., 2004). These tragedies call for continued efforts to develop new theories and strategies for understanding and possibly reducing car-accident injuries and fatalities.

Haddon, Suchman, and Klein (1964) argued that it is important to exploit the power of social theory for investigating road safety. Zaidel (1992) continued this argument, stating that it is important to understand the relationship between the behavior of the individual and that of other drivers in the social context. The reason is that all drivers are influenced by the environment - by other road users, by general social norms, and by traffic laws that dictate the interactional aspects of driving (see, e.g., Dannefer, 1977). These calls were restated by

Connolly and Aberg (1993), who explored social comparison and contagion models; and by Bjorklund and Aberg (2005), who investigated the influence of other drivers' behavior on a driver's behavior at intersections. Huguenin recently criticized the individually focused approach, "whereby the individual tends towards specific modes of behaviour based on his attitudes and/or his personality and whose behaviour can be modified individually or at least reliably diagnosed" (2005: 7). He argued that "in the area of general prevention and intervention, the individually focused approach must rightly and increasingly be abandoned and preference given to a social one" (2005: 7).

The importance of the social factor becomes clear when looking at road accident data. These show that a significant proportion of the accidents are collisions involving interaction between drivers or between a driver and a pedestrian. In the United States, for example, 68% of the accidents are collisions between vehicles (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2004). In Britain that year, 85% of fatal and severe accidents were collisions between cars (69%) or between a car and a pedestrian (15%) (Department for Transport, 2004). In Israel, 73% of all accidents with injuries are collision accidents and 15% are pedestrian accidents (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2005). These figures bear testimony to the failure of interaction on the road.

The social component of driving and road accidents is also revealed in studies that examined the manner in which drivers acquired their driving ability. It seems that, as with other social and other cultural skills, the family is a significant agent of socialization, transmitting to young drivers the norms of driving and accepted cultural driving habits. The driver acquires most

driving skills from the family through observing the driving of parents and their life style in general (Carlson and Klein, 1970; Preusser et al., 1985; Taubman Ben-Ari et al., 2005).

According to Lupton (2002), little sociological research has been published on driving or car culture. There are, however, studies that examined the differences in road accident involvement among different social groups. Nevertheless, most such studies are not grounded in sociological theory. Furthermore, researchers often explain their findings as a social or cultural phenomenon without empirically examining their argument (see, e.g., Leviakangas, 1998). The reason that socio-cultural aspects are not fully explored in studies of road safety is that culture is largely taken for granted, is immersed in experience, and is therefore invisible and difficult to study (Swidler, 2001). Furthermore, cultural analysis is perhaps complex, as there is no agreement on the boundaries of the domain (Mattaini, 1996). Although cultural aspects are difficult to measure and to manipulate through intervention, we nevertheless propose that it is possible to explore the effects of cultural factors on road safety through simulation, as well as statistical and laboratory research.

The objective of the present article is to propose a model that includes a theoretical sociological explanation for "Social Accidents" - collisions that involve two or more drivers. Although a distinction is made between single-car accidents, which may be defined as "individual accidents," and "social accidents," a single-vehicle accident might clearly include social characteristics as will be presented in the sections to follow; for instance, if a young driver falls asleep at the wheel on a weekend night, this might be the result of an exaggerated sense of one's driving ability and non-appreciation of the level of danger of night driving, two

characteristics that typify younger drivers. However, since collisions between drivers are more frequent than individual accidents, the authors decided to concentrate on the former.

The model benefits from prior research, which has found between-group differences in various areas of road safety - accident involvement (Norris et al., 2000), attitudes toward road safety (Yagil, 1999), use of seat belts (Calisir and Lehto, 2002; Vivoda et al., 2004), crossing an intersection on a red light (Porter and England, 2000), traveling over the speed limit (Gabany et al., 1997), among others. The central argument here is that road accidents are embedded in a social context; therefore, group differences in risky driving stem in part from cultural differences between populations. Although these differences do not directly imply that car-accidents are due to social interaction, they might lead to the possibility that an encounter between drivers from different cultures with different points of view and norms of behavior could increase the probability of a road accident. Groups in this context refers to nations as well as to the variety of groups within nations, such as women and men, young drivers and older drivers, education groups, income groups, religious and ethnic groups.

The model suggests that the interaction between two or more drivers could be examined as a function of the reciprocal relationship between society and culture at the macro level and attitudes and behaviors of drivers at the micro level. This approach might shed new light on road accidents in suggesting that they result in part from socialization processes and internalized behaviors, all of which are manifested in decision-making while driving and interacting with other drivers.

Following the presentation of the model, we will review a series of studies on road safety to demonstrate the existence of cultural differences among various population groups between

and within nations. This survey was conducted in order to examine which social characteristics have been tested over the years. The article next presents prevailing theories of culture and some of their application to traffic-safety research. The paper ends by demonstrating how cultural facets could help explain "Social Accidents" and by assessing the possible contribution of the model to the study and prevention of road accidents.

2. The "Social Accident" model

Sociological and anthropological studies assess cultural differences among different groups – differences between nations, and between groups within nations, such as between women and men and among social classes. These differences can affect different transport perceptions and cause difficulties in inter-driver communication, thus leading to the increased probability of an accident. According to Swidler (1986; 2001), culture influences action through shaping a behavioral repertoire or "tool kit" that includes habits, skills, and styles that people employ to build "strategies of action." Every group has its own "tool kit" and particular cultural characteristics that cause its members to interpret the environment and to make decisions in a particular manner. Accordingly, drivers who belong to different groups might diverge in interpreting similar events while driving and, consequently, make conflicting decisions, thereby increasing the risks of their being involved in an accident. (Obviously there are different levels of homogeneity within groups. Yet, as was suggested by Burt (2005), it is reasonable to assume that, on average, heterogeneity within groups is smaller than between groups.)

Driving involves a high level of coordination, decision-making, and a certain level of skill (Gusfield, 1981). It includes interaction and communication between drivers (Shor, 1964), and it is based on trust. In driving, strangers "flow" with one another through the help of common

laws while communicating with joint symbols (Urry, 2004). Communication among drivers clarifies intentions and so lessens misunderstanding, frustration, and conflict among drivers; it also creates a more predictable driving environment. An individual who does not internalize social standards and does not share the same culture is thus putting both himself and others at risk (Zaidel, 1992). The situation may be compared to language. An individual who wants to be understood by others must act according to the accepted rules of the language (Elias, 1995). If one disregards these rules and action strategies, the speaker or writer will not be understood (Swidler, 2001). So it is on the road. The moment drivers do not understand each other, the environment becomes less predictable and the probability of an accident rises – as was mentioned by Stinchcombe, who stated that "when people's activities are not integrated in the system, they crash into each other" (1975: 27). The significance of cultural differences and gaps in communication are strikingly revealed when people drive in foreign countries (Edensor, 2004). On the other hand, drivers who share the same culture might have similar "tools kits," hence interpreting the environment in a similar manner; this, in turn, might enhance communication with each other and eventually reduce the probability of car-accidents. It may be assumed, therefore, that interactions among drivers from different groups increases the probability of an accident. According to the model presented in Figure 1, an accident is influenced directly by environmental characteristics (road design, weather, etc.) and by drivers' behavior, with the latter being influenced by individual and cultural characteristic. Drivers from one group (e.g., those with low levels of education) may have a particular driving repertoire that defines perceptions and norms of behavior differ that from those of a driver from another group (e.g., those with high levels of education). This cultural mismatch may lead to taking

different strategies of action, interpreting a situation differently, and so to making even conflicting decisions, and to other particular behavior on the road, whether slowing down, accelerating, deviating from the lane, looking in the rear or side-view mirror, etc. These multiple culturally-influenced decisions are exacerbated by uncertainty, the presence of passengers in the vehicle, and the speed needed to make a decision. However, the Social Accidents model suggests that for the most part, drivers from different groups eventually behave in similar ways without conflict.

[Figure 1 about here]

The model implies that when drivers from different groups arrive at a non-signalized intersection, each driver will have his/her unique attitudes, as well as road behaviors, for each draws driving strategies from a different tool kit. To the extent that drivers perceive and interpret the situation a little differently from one another, communication between them may be defective, thereby increasing the risk that an accident will occur. Examples of such communication problems and misunderstandings are narrated in the following story (source: “Stories from Life,” an internet site of the Israel National Authority for Road Safety):

I was returning from school in the direction of my house, traveling along the main road, on which the right of way was mine. I came to the intersection of the main road and, naturally, I slowed down, because there will always be those who try to merge into the traffic and take the right of way from you. There were two cars at the intersection that wanted to merge into the flow, so I began to slow down even more, but I saw that they had stopped and, therefore, I began to move...until I saw that he was cutting me off. It was already too late, and I felt him suddenly go into me, and my car...he ruined the whole left part of the car. (Or, 2005).

This example hints that different group norms influenced the behavior of the drivers – one was a man, the other a woman (Bourdieu, 2001). As the model suggests, the woman who drove on the main road based her behavior on a feminine tool kit. She believed that traffic laws should always be obeyed (Yagil, 1999) and was more anxious while driving (Taubman Ben-Ari et al.,

2004). As a result, she thought that she had the right of way. In contrast, the masculine driver (Bourdieu, 2001) drew on aggressive norms of driving (Turner et al., 1975) and therefore maintained less distance between the cars (Wennel and Cooper, 1981). Hence, he expected the other driver to allow him to merge into traffic. These different group norms may have produced problems of communication between the drivers and set the stage for this specific road accident.

Here is another scenario: Two drivers, the first age 44, and the second 21. The two make conflicting decisions at the end of the green light (Factor et al., 2006). The model suggests that the two drivers might draw their behavior from their different cultural tool kits. The adult driver follows his group-specific norm, which gives importance to traffic laws (Yagil, 1999), leading him to stop at a red light. Research suggests that young drivers possess an exaggerated sense of their driving ability, leading them to speed up in such situations (Hemenway and Solnick, 1993). Consequently a younger driver speeding up and an older driver slowing down produce a norm-caused conflict that might lead to an accident between them.

3. Explanation of the Model

3.1. Intergroup Differences in Road Accidents

Prior studies – that vary by discipline, country, and methodology – have shown that national differences exist in different aspects of road accidents. The fascinating study by Stanford (1985) on driving characteristics in Egypt and the study by Edensor (2004) examining driving habits in Britain and India show that driving is culture-dependent: driving practices in these different countries vary, and one cannot point to a uniform, global pattern of driving; rather, different countries have different driving codes of behavior (Featherstone, 2004). Compared

with countries in the West, both Egypt and India have a low level of legislation and formal enforcement, a fact that necessitates informal agreements and driving rules among drivers.

Thus, for example:

In Alexandria, when a driver wishes to proceed west by pulling out into traffic onto Rue Mustafa Kamel from a side street, he will appear not to wait for an open space in the mass of movement, but will simply plunge ahead (Stanford, 1985: 344).

Sivak and colleagues (Sivak, Soler et al., 1989a, b; Sivak, Soler, Trankle et al., 1989) examined a series of studies of inter-cultural differences in the United States, Spain, Germany, and Brazil. They found differences among the countries in drivers' self-evaluation, perception, and risk-taking. For instance, when participants in an experiment were asked to “cross” a computer-simulated intersection, Germans were found to take fewer risks than Americans and Spanish drivers. Shinar et al. (2003) examined the extent of understanding of traffic signs in Canada, Finland, Israel, and Poland. The investigators found large differences among countries in people’s understanding of traffic signs, caused in part by cultural differences. Further, Shinar (1998) argued that cultural norms influenced the extent of expected aggressiveness, norms that change both between countries and within a country.

In addition, there is evidence of driving-culture differences within countries among sub-groups according to gender, age, education, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status. While most studies have tended to look at these variables as individual level characteristics, we focused our attention on cultural aspects relating to these group differences and highlighted the diverse mechanisms that might affect safety behavior.

Gender has been identified in various studies as a clear factor in predicting road accident involvement (Yagil, 1999). In almost every measure of road accident involvement in the United States since 1980, it was found, the rate of male involvement was double that of the

females (Hemenway and Solnick, 1993; Norris et al., 2000); moreover, men had many more traffic violations than did women (Ferguson et al., 2001).

The literature shows that young age constitutes the principal explanatory parameter for the death of people between the ages of 15 and 29 (Ferguson et al., 2001; Gusfield, 1981; Sivak, 2002). It seems that young people possess an exaggerated sense of their driving ability, which apparently leads them to a non-appreciation of the level of danger connected with different driving actions and, then, to taking many more risks while driving (DeJoy, 1992; Gabany et al., 1997). Young people perceive traffic laws as less important than do older people (Yagil, 1999), and take less care in buckling up with a seat belt (Eby et al., 2002).

Braver (2003) found that higher occupant mortality rates per unit of travel were observed among persons with less education (even after controlling for reported belt-use). According to Hasselberg, Vaez, and Laflamme (2005), younger drivers with low education levels have the highest risk of suffering a severe injury, as well as the highest risk of being involved in any type of accident.

Various studies have found a relationship between driving violations, perceptions of risk, and accident involvement, on the one hand, and ethnic groups and socioeconomic conditions, on the other (Ferguson et al., 2002; Stiles and Grieshop, 1999; Vredenburg and Cohen, 1995). In Arizona, for example, the fatality rate from road accidents differs among the different ethnic groups - Indian Americans were found to have the highest risk of dying in an auto accident (Outcalt et al., 2003). In Israel, drivers from the non-Jewish sector were involved in 26% of all serious and fatal car-accidents in 2001, though they constituted only 12% of all licensed drivers (National Road Safety Authority, 2004). Similar to these ethnic differences, Dobson et al.

(1999) found that women in Australia who were born in non-English-speaking countries (i.e., immigrants) had a higher risk of being involved in road accidents than did Australian English-speaking women.

Low per-capita income has also been identified as a determinant of injury mortality (Braver, 2003). Hasselberg et al. (2005), for example, found that the types and severity of road accidents varied among different socioeconomic classes. Shin, Hong, and Waldron (1999) showed that fastening seat belts was related to the socioeconomic condition of the individual and to one's ethnicity. According to Wells et al. (2002), drivers from lower socioeconomic backgrounds are less likely to use seat belts. On the other hand, another finding (Shinar et al., 2001) was that drivers with low incomes maintained permitted speed levels more than did those with high incomes.

3.2. A Socio-Cultural Explanation for Road Accidents

The question remains how road accidents can be explained sociologically. We propose to extend Durkheim's study of suicide (Durkheim, 1952), which showed that the collective tendencies of a society affected the individual's tendency to suicide exogenously. Looking at road accidents, we suggest that social causes at the macro level – such as cultural differences – might account for the attitudes and behaviors of drivers and their relationship to road accidents on the micro level. Thus, we hypothesize that cultural differences produce varying modes of driving, so that an encounter on the road between drivers from different groups might lead to road accidents.

No agreement exists among sociologists and anthropologists as to the definition and meaning of the concept of “culture” (Alexander and Smith, 2001; Kroeber and Kluckhohn, 1963; Kuper,

1999; Swidler, 1986). Tylor (1871) defined culture as including knowledge, beliefs, art, ethics, law, and all other abilities and habits necessary for a person to be a member of society. Geertz (1973) argues that human beings are incomplete animals who gain overall completion through culture, especially the specific culture in which they live.

One of the most influential researchers in the area of culture in the past few decades is Ann Swidler. In her book, *Talk of Love* (2001), Swidler asks how people use culture and how culture influences their actions. In her opinion, people use only some of the culture available to them and they employ cultural tools in various ways. Her central argument is that culture influences action, not by giving values, which are internalized in any activity, but by shaping a repertoire (like that of an actor, musician, or dancer) or “tool kit,” which contains habits, skills, and styles. With this tool kit, people construct “strategies of action,” which provide a number of general ways of solving problems - solutions that are appropriate for a variety of problems. Culture, then, influences social activity because it supports or limits the individual’s strategies of action.

DiMaggio (1997) integrates the sociological theory of culture with the theories of cognitive psychology. It is his contention that some of the “tool kit,” or repertoire of behaviors and norms, also contains schemes found in people’s heads. The schemes are representations of complex cultural phenomena that shape the form in which we approach, interpret, remember, and respond to information that reaches us. Culture includes many schemes, of which we choose the most suitable for a situation on the basis of hints given in the environment.

A society includes a large of number of sub-cultures or groups: ethnic group, socioeconomic stratification, gender, and so forth (Blau, 1977; Clarke et al., 1997). Almost everyone belongs

to a number of sub-groups (overlapping or intersecting) and can participate in each to different degrees and strengths (Arnold, 1970a; Blau, 1977). Every such group has cultural traits and mechanisms that are unique to it and that include norms, behavioral expectations, life style, and an attitude framework, all of which differ to some extent from those of other groups and from the characteristics of the society at large. These cultural mechanisms differentiate the members of a particular group from those who are members of other groups and influence decision-making and group members' activity (Arnold, 1970b; Blau, 1977; Gelder and Thornton, 1997; Irwin, 1997). Bourdieu (1989) suggests comparing social space to a geographical space that is divided into regions. The closer the individual or groups are to one another in this space, the more characteristics they will possess in common; whereas the more distant they are, the fewer they will have in common.

Obviously there are different levels of homogeneity within groups. However, if we look at a group or a sub-culture as having a mean and a standard deviation, as Arnold (1970a) suggested, we could assume that, in general, the standard deviation within a group would be smaller than the standard deviation between groups (Burt, 2005). Hence, on average two randomly chosen members of a specific group would be more similar to each other than would two randomly chosen members from different groups. On the other hand, sub-cultures do have some shared elements with society at large (Arnold, 1970a). In this sense, it might be possible to compute cultural heterogeneity indices for countries and to assess the correlation between these measures and national rates of accidents. It would also be possible to compute group heterogeneity measures within a nation and to correlate them with group risk.

3.2.1. *Examples of applications of culture to traffic safety*

Research of the applications of culture to traffic safety and of cultural design and its effects on behavior can be found in a variety of fields. Wells et al. (2000) studied the use of feedback signs to motivate seat belt use located in a shopping center and found that the feedback program increased drivers' seat belt use by 10%. Geller and colleagues demonstrated in a series of studies and in a variety of settings – e.g., a university campus (Geller et al., 1989), industrial sites (Boyce and Geller, 1999; Geller, 1983), and pizza deliverers (Ludwig and Geller, 1999) – that different kinds of incentives, such as seat belt promotion fliers that could be exchanged for prizes (Geller, 1983) and signing a pledge card committing people to buckle up (Geller et al., 1989), could successfully increase safety belt usage.

There is also some evidence that different law-enforcement systems influence different groups in different ways. If we consider law as part of the normative system embedded in culture, we could say that culture might eventually have an effect on drivers. Wells, Williams, and Farmer (2002), for example, found that there were no differences in belt use across racial groups for both males and females in cities with a primary seat-belt law. However, in secondary law cities (see Eby et al., 2002 for an explanation of secondary law), Black males were significantly less likely to use belts than were either Hispanic males or White males. Similarly, Eby et al. (2002) argued that standard enforcement apparently decreased the gap in safety-belt use between high and low-use groups.

The literature provides examples of the influence of cultural intervention in other fields of study. Data suggests that alcohol addiction can be dramatically affected through cultural design. The Community Reinforcement Approach (CRA) is an "example of the power of

cultural design, and also a clear example of how interlocking contingencies among cultural entities can stand in the way of effective responses to social problems" (Mattaini, 1996: 35).

3.2.2. *How can culture aid in explaining "Social Accidents"?*

Culture has a number of special characteristics. It includes collective representations – vocabularies, symbols, and codes (Eliasoph and Lichterman, 2003); it is a repertoire and a “tool kit” - habits, skills, and styles (Swidler, 2001); it has norms and values; and, it includes, as well, the schemes that exist in the head of its members (DiMaggio, 1997). All these elements structure the ability of individuals to think and act. With the aid of existing cultural tools, individuals construct their worldview and their attitudes and posit assumptions about the world surrounding them. With the help of these assumptions and perceptions, they evaluate reality and interpret their environment. Since culture differs from society to society and from group to group, it may be assumed that people from different cultures and groups will behave in a different manner in a similar situation, because different cultures lead to different interpretations of the environment and, in the end, perhaps also to different behaviors.

Leviakangas (1998) defines “traffic culture” as the sum total of factors influencing the skills, attitudes, and behavior of the driver. Traffic culture is the consequence both of cultural traditions and of economic and political contexts (Hayakawa et al., 2000; Summala, 1985; Zaidel, 1992). In other words, similar to the general characteristics of the concept of culture, traffic culture - which may be different in different groups and societies - has an effect on general perceptions of the traffic system and on the style of driving, as well as – in the end – on the individual’s behavior in a specific situation while driving. Nevertheless, it is important to mention that regardless of this cultural explanation, there might be some degree of variance

among members of the same group because of individual driver histories (Boyce and Geller, 1999).

One may surmise, as our research model suggests, that the probability of an accident occurrence increases in interactions among drivers from different cultures and groups. This is due to the fact that these drivers may have a different repertoire and tool kit that define for them different points of view and norms of behavior. The result, as mentioned earlier, are, different strategies of action, different interpretations of the situation, particularistic decision-making, and other types of behavior on the road.

4. Discussion and Summary

This paper examines interactions among drivers with the aid of a theoretical model that explains "Social Accidents." The explanation is motivated by the findings of many research studies, surveyed above, that show differences among groups in various areas of road safety. These differences in road accident involvement, in attitudes, and in behaviors related to driving are found within nations, between men and women, between youth and adults, and between different ethnic and socioeconomic groups. Instead of examining the individual driver, however, the model proposes to observe the *interaction* among drivers.

It seems that sociological theory in general and the theory of the "tool kit" in particular could contribute to an understanding of interactions among drivers that may lead to new directions in reducing road accidents. The "Social Accidents" model proposed here could be examined empirically in future research in order to impart insights in regard to the social mechanism related to interaction and communication among drivers and to the tool kit of drivers coming from different social groups.

For example, a future statistical study that would link accident data with census data (see, e.g., Braver, 2003) might examine the social and demographic characteristics of two drivers (or more) who were involved in collisions. Such a study might be able to test the "Social Accident" model empirically by determining whether collisions between drivers from different social and cultural groups (e.g., men vs. women or high socioeconomic level vs. low socioeconomic level) are random in nature, or whether the probability that drivers from the same group (e.g., men vs. men or high vs. high socioeconomic level) will collide with each other has a lower probability of a collision than that between drivers from different groups. If the probability of a collision between drivers from different cultural and social groups is higher, it might be the case that different cultural tool kits, among other things, influenced the occurrence of the collision.

Furthermore, computer simulations or a qualitative in-depth and interpretive approaches aimed at exploring the tool kits of these different groups could be designed. As Lupton (2002) did in connection with road-rage, it might be helpful to interview drivers from different groups in order to provide detailed insights into their respective cultural tool kits and driving experiences.

The findings of these studies might enable the development of tools to improve communicability among drivers - whether through human means or through technological means - and so contribute to the prevention of road accidents. Thus it would be possible, for example, to construct special educational training programs for novice drivers, each focused on a different social group. These programs would be written in cooperation with the groups themselves (Porter and England, 2000; Vivoda et al., 2004) and conveyed to each group in a different form in order to be suitable for the particular group's tool kit. "Minor changes in driver behavior can prevent injury and save lives" (Boyce and Geller, 2002: 51). Hence, one of

the main targets of these training programs would be, not to "change their culture," but to add more "tools" to the group's repertoire in order to lessen gaps in perception and communication and to homogenize the driving tool kit of different groups. Further, it might be fruitful to teach drivers to look also at the human driver rather than just at the car (Dannefer, 1977). In this way, when drivers from different cultures approach an intersection, they might understand the situation in the same way and anticipate the other driver's maneuvers, thus perhaps reducing the probability of collision.

Moreover, it might be helpful, too, as was suggested by Boyce and Geller (2002), to identify classes of driving behaviors and cultural practices in each social group. Afterward, different levels of cultural design (Mattaini, 1996) might be applied in different social groups with the intention of intervening in a behavior that will have concomitant effects on other behaviors (Boyce and Geller, 2002; Ludwig and Geller, 1999).

Clearly, as Williams and Wells (2004) saw, education is not enough. It is important to accompany such programs with mass publicity about the existence of group differences, and to heighten awareness of enforcement. In any event, awareness of culture may be life saving; ignoring it might prove fatal.

Figures

Figure 1: **Research Model - The Social Accident Mechanism**

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank Prof. Ann Swidler for her helpful comments in regard to her theory.

This paper was written with the support of the Israel Ministry of Science and Technology and the Israel National Road Safety Authority and with the aid of the Ran Naor Fund for Advancing Road Safety Research of the Or Yarok (Green Light) organization.

References

- Alexander, J.C., and P. Smith. 2001. The Strong Program in Cultural Theory In: Handbook of Sociological Theory, edited by Jonathan H. Turner. Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers, New York, Pp. 135-150.
- Arnold, D.O. 1970a. Subculture Marginality. In: Subcultures, edited by David O. Arnold. The Glendessary Press, Berkeley, Pp. 81-89.
- (Ed.). 1970b. Subcultures. The Glendessary Press, Berkeley.
- Bjorklund, G.M., and L. Aberg. 2005. Driver Behaviour in Intersections: Formal and Informal Traffic Rules. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behavior* 8, 239-253.
- Blau, P.M. 1977. *Inequality and Heterogeneity*. Collier Macmillan Publishing Co. Inc., New York.
- Bourdieu, P. 1989. Social Space and Symbolic Power. *Sociological Theory* 7, 14-25.
- . 2001. *Masculine Domination*. Stanford University Press, Stanford, Calif.
- Boyce, T.E., and E.S. Geller. 1999. Attempts to Increase Vehicle Safety-Belt Use among Industry Workers: What Can We Learn from Our Failures? *Journal of Organizational Behavior Management* 19, 27-44.
- . 2002. An Instrumented Vehicle Assessment of Problem Behavior and Driving Style: Do Younger Males Really Take More Risks? *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 34, 51-64.
- Braver, E.R. 2003. Race, Hispanic Origin, and Socioeconomic Status in Relation to Motor Vehicles Occupant Death Rates and Risk Factors among Adults. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 35, 295-309.
- Burt, R.S. 2005. *Brokerage and Closure : An Introduction to Social Capital*. Oxford University Press, Oxford ; New York.
- Calisir, F., and M.P. Lehto. 2002. Young Drivers' Decision Making and Safety Belt Use. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 34, 793-805.
- Carlson, W.L., and D. Klein. 1970. Familiar Vs. Institutional Socialization of the Young Traffic Offender. *Journal of Safety Research* 2, 13-25.
- Central Bureau of Statistics. 2005. *Road Accidents with Casualties 2004, Part: General Summaries (in Hebrew)*. Central Bureau of Statistics, Jerusalem.
- Clarke, J., S. Hall, T. Jefferson, and B. Roberts. 1997. Subcultures, Cultures and Class. In: *The Subcultures Reader*, edited by Ken Gelder and Sarah Thornton. Routledge, London and New York, Pp. 100-111.
- Connolly, T., and L. Aberg. 1993. Some Contagion Models of Speeding. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 25, 57-66.
- Dannefer, W.D. 1977. Driving and Symbolic Interaction. *Sociological Inquiry* 47, 33-38.
- DeJoy, D.M. 1992. An Examination of Gender Differences in Traffic Accident Risk Perception. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 24, 237-246.
- Department for Transport. 2004. *Transport Statistics Great Britain : 2004*. TSO Publications, London.
- DiMaggio, P. 1997. Culture and Cognition. *Annual Review of Sociology* 23, 263-287.

- Dobson, A., W. Brown, J. Ball, J. Powers, and M. McFadden. 1999. Women Drivers' Behavior, Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Accidents. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 31, 525-535.
- Durkheim, E. 1952. *Suicide, a Study in Sociology*. Routledge & K. Paul, London,.
- Eby, D.W., J.M. Vivoda, and T.A. Fordyce. 2002. The Effects of Standard Enforcement on Michigan Safety Belt Use. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 34, 815-823.
- Edensor, T. 2004. Automobility and National Identity - Representation, Geography and Driving Practice. *Theory Culture and Society* 21, 101-120.
- Elias, N. 1995. Technization and Civilization. *Theory Culture and Society* 12, 7-42.
- Eliasoph, N., and P. Lichterman. 2003. Culture in Interaction. *American Journal of Sociology* 108, 735-794.
- Elvik, R., and T. Vaa (Eds.). 2004. *The Handbook of Road Safety Measures*. Elsevier, Amsterdam ; New York.
- Factor, R., J.N. Prashker, and D. Mahalel. 2006. Flashing Green: The Gap between Public Perception and Theoretical Safety Evaluation. Paper presented to the Traffic and Road Safety Third International Congress.
- Featherstone, M. 2004. Automobilities - an Introduction. *Theory Culture and Society* 21, 1-24.
- Ferguson, S.A., M.M. Burns, D. Fiorentino, A.F. Williams, and J. Garcia. 2002. Drinking and Driving among Mexican American and Non-Hispanic White Males in Long Beach, California. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 34, 429-437.
- Ferguson, S.A., A.F. Williams, J.F. Chapline, D.W. Reinfurt, and D.M. De Leonardis. 2001. Relationship of Parent Driving Records to the Driving Records of Their Children. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 33, 229-234.
- Gabany, S.G., P. Plummer, and P. Grigg. 1997. Why Drivers Speed: The Speeding Perception Inventory. *Journal of Safety Research* 28, 29-36.
- Geertz, C. 1973. *The Interpretation of Cultures; Selected Essays*. Basic Books, New York,.
- Gelder, K., and S. Thornton (Eds.). 1997. *The Subcultures Reader*. Routledge, London and New York.
- Geller, E.S. 1983. Rewarding Safety Belt Usage at an Industrial-Setting: Tests of Treatment Generality and Response Maintenance. *Journal of Applied Behavior Analysis* 16, 189-202.
- Geller, E.S., M.J. Kalsher, J.R. Rudd, and G.R. Lehman. 1989. Promoting Safety Belt Use on a University Campus: An Integration of Commitment and Incentive Strategies. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology* 19, 3-19.
- Gusfield, J.R. 1981. *The Culture of Public Problems: Drinking-Driving and the Symbolic Order*. The University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London.
- Haddon, W., E.A. Suchman, and D. Klein (Eds.). 1964. *Accident Research: Methods and Approaches*. Harper and Row, New York.
- Hasselberg, M., M. Vaez, and L. Laflamme. 2005. Socioeconomic Aspects of the Circumstances and Consequences of Car Crashes among Young Adults. *Social Science & Medicine* 60, 287-295.
- Hayakawa, H., P.S. Fischbeck, and B. Fischhoff. 2000. Traffic Accident Statistics and Risk Perceptions in Japan and the Unites States. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 32, 827-835.

- Hemenway, D., and S.J. Solnick. 1993. Fuzzy Dice, Dream Cars, and Indecent Gestures: Correlates of Driver Behavior? *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 25, 161-170.
- Huguenin, R.D. 2005. Traffic Psychology in a (New) Social Setting. In: *Traffic and Transport Psychology : Theory and Application*, edited by Geoffrey Underwood. Elsevier, Amsterdam ; London, Pp. xii, 621 p.
- Irwin, J. 1997. Notes on the Present Status of the Concept Subculture. In: *The Subcultures Reader*, edited by Ken Gelder and Sarah Thornton. Routledge, London and New York, Pp. 66-70.
- Kroeber, A.L., and C. Kluckhohn. 1963. *Culture: A Critical Review of Concepts and Definitions*. Vintage books New York.
- Kuper, A. 1999. *Culture : The Anthropologists' Account*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Leviakangas, P. 1998. Accident Risk of Foreign Drivers - the Case of Russian Drivers in South-Eastern Finland. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 30, 245-254.
- Ludwig, T.D., and E.S. Geller. 1999. Behavior Change among Agents of a Community Safety Program: Pizza Deliverers Advocate Community Safety Belt Use. *Journal of Organizational Behavior Management* 19, 3-24.
- Lupton, D. 2002. Road Rage: Drivers' Understandings and Experiences. *Journal of Sociology* 38, 275-290.
- Mattaini, M.A. 1996. Public Issues, Human Behavior, and Cultural Design. In: *Finding Solutions to Social Problems : Behavioral Strategies for Change*, edited by Mark A. Mattaini and Bruce A. Thyer. American Psychological Association, Washington, DC, Pp. 13-40.
- National Highway Traffic Safety Administration. 2004. *Traffic Safety Facts*. U.S Department of Transportation, Washington, D.C.
- National Road Safety Authority. 2004. *The Characteristics and Causes of Road Accidents in the Non-Jewish Sector (in Hebrew)*. National Road Safety Authority, Jerusalem.
- Norris, F.H., A.B. Matthews, and J.K. Riad. 2000. Characterological, Situational, and Behavioral Risk Factors for Motor Vehicle Accidents: A Prospective Examination. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 32, 505-515.
- Or. 2005. Simply Awful (in Hebrew). Online posting. Israeli Road Safety Authority - stories from life
<<http://bdold.mot.gov.il/SipurimMehachayim/ShowSipur.asp?Hod=140&appid=6>>.
- Outcalt, D.C., C. Bay, A. Dellapena, and M.K. Cota. 2003. Motor Vehicle Crash Fatalities by Race/Ethnicity in Arizona, 1990-96. Pp. 251-256 in *Injury Prevention*.
- Peden, M., R. Scurfield, D. Sleet, D. Mohan, A.A. Hyder, E. Jarawan, and C. Mathers (Eds.). 2004. *World Report on Road Traffic Injury Prevention*. World Health Organization, Geneva.
- Porter, B.E., and K.J. England. 2000. Predicting Red-Light Running Behavior: A Traffic Safety Study in Three Urban Settings. *Journal of Safety Research* 31, 1-8.
- Preusser, D.F., A.F. Williams, and A.K. Lund. 1985. Parental Role in Teenage Driving. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 14, 73-84.
- Shin, D., L. Hong, and I. Waldron. 1999. Possible Causes of Socioeconomic and Ethnic Differences in Seat Belt Use among High School Students. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 31, 485-496.

- Shinar, D. 1978. *Psychology on the Road: The Human Factor in Traffic Safety*. John Wiley and Sons, New York.
- . 1998. Aggressive Driving: The Contribution of the Drivers and Situation. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behavior* 1, 137-160.
- Shinar, D., R.E. Dewar, H. Summala, and L. Zakowska. 2003. Traffic Symbol Comprehension: A Cross-Cultural Study. *Ergonomics* 46, 1549-1565.
- Shinar, D., E. Schechtman, and R. Compton. 2001. Self-Reports of Safe Driving Behaviors in Relationship to, Sex, Age, Education and Income in the Us Adult Driving Population. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 33, 111-116.
- Shor, R.E. 1964. Shared Patterns of Nonverbal Normative Expectations in Automobile Driving. *Journal of Social Psychology* 62, 155-163.
- Sivak, M. 2002. How Common Sense Fails Us on the Road: Contribution of Bounded Rationality to the Annual Worldwide Toll of One Million Traffic Fatalities. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behavior* 5, 259-269.
- Sivak, M., J. Soler, and U. Trankle. 1989a. Cross-Cultural Differences in Driver Risk-Taking. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 21, 363-369.
- . 1989b. Cross-Cultural Differences in Driver Self Assessment. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 21, 371-375.
- Sivak, M., J. Soler, U. Trankle, and J.M. Spanghol. 1989. Cross-Cultural Differences in Driver Risk Perception. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 21, 355-362.
- Stanford, G.W. 1985. Auto Traffic in Egypt as a Verdant Grammar. *Social Psychology Quarterly* 48, 337-348.
- Stiles, M.C., and J.I. Grieshop. 1999. Impacts of Culture on Driver Knowledge and Safety Device Usage among Hispanic Farm Workers. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 31, 235-241.
- Stinchcombe, A.L. 1975. Parsonian Theory of Traffic Accidents. *Sociological Inquiry* 45, 27-30.
- Summala, H. 1985. Modeling Driver Behavior: A Pessimistic Prediction? In: *Human Behavior and Traffic Safety* edited by Leonard Evans and Richard C. Schwing. Plenum Press, New York, Pp. 171-178.
- Swidler, A. 1986. Culture in Action: Symbols and Strategies. *American Sociological Review* 51, 273-286.
- . 2001. *Talk of Love*. The University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London.
- Taubman Ben-Ari, O., M. Mikulincer, and O. Gillath. 2004. The Multidimensional Driving Style Inventory - Scale Construct and Validation. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 36, 323-332.
- . 2005. From Parents to Children - Similarity in Parents and Offspring Driving Styles. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behavior* 8, 19-29.
- Turner, C.W., J.F. Layton, and L.S. Simons. 1975. Naturalistic Studies of Aggressive-Behavior - Aggressive Stimuli, Victim Visibility, and Horn Honking. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 31, 1098-1107.
- Tylor, E.B. 1871. *Primitive Culture* Boston.
- Urry, J. 2004. The 'System' of Automobility. *Theory Culture and Society* 21, 25-39.
- Vivoda, J.M., D.W. Eby, and L.P. Kostyniuk. 2004. Differences in Safety Belt Use by Race. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 36, 1105-1109.

- Vredenburg, A.G., and H.H. Cohen. 1995. Does Culture Affect Risk Perception? Paper presented to the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society 39th Annual Meeting.
- Wells, J.K., J.E.L. Malenfant, A.F. Williams, and R. Van Houten. 2000. Use of a Community Program to Increase Seat Belt Use among Shopping Center Patrons in Charlotte, North Carolina. *Journal of Safety Research* 31, 93-99.
- Wells, J.K., A.F. Williams, and C.M. Farmer. 2002. Seat Belt Use among African Americans, Hispanics, and Whites. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 34, 523-529.
- Wenkel, J., and D.F. Cooper. 1981. Vehicle and Driver Effects on Junction Gap Acceptance. *Traffic Engineering and Control* 22, 628-632.
- Williams, A.F., and J.K. Wells. 2004. The Role of Enforcement Programs in Increasing Seat Belt Use. *Journal of Safety Research* 35, 175-180.
- Yagil, D. 1999. Gender and Age-Related Differences in Attitudes Towards Traffic Laws and Traffic Violations. *Transportation Research Part F* 1, 123-135.
- Zaidel, D.M. 1992. A Modeling Perspective on the Culture of Driving. *Accident Analysis and Prevention* 24, 585-597.